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Solidarity in the Asylum Procedures: The Solidarity Pool under the EU Pact on Migration and Asylum

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1. Introduction

Solidarity occupies a central position as a principle within the European Union's constitutional and political framework. It has long been regarded as a fundamental value underpinning cooperation among Member States and facilitating the pursuit of common objectives. Nowhere is the importance of solidarity more evident than in the fields of migration and asylum, where uneven geographical exposure to migratory flows has generated persistent debates regarding responsibility-sharing among Member States. Although consecrated in Article 80 TFEU¹ solidarity became effective with the adoption of the 2024 EU Pact on Migration and Asylum.

This policy brief examines the role and evolution of solidarity within migration and asylum policy in the context of the Pact, looking into the application of solidarity in the first year of its operationalisation, 2026. It analyses in particular the different concepts of solidarity – and in practice the lack thereof, especially in what is termed as “people’s solidarity” – during the previous migration crises of the EU, as well as the reforms introduced through the New Pact on Migration and Asylum and the longer-term implications of the new solidarity mechanism. The paper further discusses the challenges associated with translating the

¹ ‘The policies of the Union set out in this Chapter and their implementation shall be governed by the principle of solidarity and fair sharing of responsibility, including its financial implications, between the Member States. Whenever necessary, the Union acts adopted pursuant to this Chapter shall contain appropriate measures to give effect to this principle’.

principle of solidarity into effective policy instruments and assesses the initial findings emerging from the Pact's implementation.

2. The concept of solidarity in the European Union

Solidarity has been a defining feature of European integration since the establishment of the European Communities. The Schuman Declaration of 9 May 1950 already mentioned that Europe “will be built through concrete achievements which first create a de facto solidarity” (solidarité de fait). The Preamble to the Treaty Establishing the European Coal and Steel Community Treaty (1951) recognized that ‘Europe can be built only through real practical achievements which will first of all create real solidarity, and through the establishment of common bases for economic development’. Later on, ‘solidarity’ appeared in the preamble to the Single European Act (1986) and as a principle, together with ‘cohesion’ in the Maastricht Treaty (1992).²

Although initially expressed primarily through political cooperation and economic integration³, the principle gradually

² Andrea Sangiovanni, Solidarity in the European Union, *Oxford Journal of Legal Studies*, Volume 33, Issue 2, Summer 2013, p. 214.

³ In fact, as Saracino points out “*the concept lacks anchoring by a definition or operationalisable interpretation anywhere in the *acquis Communautaire*”.*

See D. Saracino, *Understanding solidarity in the European Union: an analytical framework in Theory and Society* (2024) 53, p. 1105.

acquired a more explicit constitutional dimension within the EU legal order⁴ and has been characterized as “a foundational/historical value and as an element forging the EU constitutional identity”.⁵

In the Treaty of Lisbon, solidarity is, first and foremost, reflected in Article 2 of the Treaty on European Union (TEU), which identifies the values upon which the Union is founded, including cooperation, equality, and mutual support among Member States. In addition, Article 222 TFEU, commonly known as the Solidarity Clause, provides a legal basis for joint action when a Member State faces a terrorist attack, natural disaster, or other major crises. The clause enables the Union and its Member States to mobilise available instruments and resources in a coordinated manner to prevent, respond to, and recover from emergencies.

Consequently, solidarity in the European Union functions both as a normative value and as an operational principle that guides collective action in situations where individual Member States face disproportionate challenges.

⁴ It is now consecrated, besides Article 2 TEU, in Article 3(3) TEU and Articles 67(2), 80, 122(1), 192 TFEU and 222(1) TFEU. It is also mentioned in the preambles to the TEU and constitutes the title of an entire chapter (Chapter IV) of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU.

⁵ Arban, E. (2023). The Principle of Solidarity Forging the Constitutional Identity of the European Union. In: de Poorter, J., van der Schyff, G., Stremmer, M., De Visser, M., Leijten, I., van Oirsouw, C. (eds) *European Yearbook of Constitutional Law 2022*. European Yearbook of Constitutional Law, vol 4. T.M.C. Asser Press, The Hague.

3. Solidarity in migration and asylum

In the context of migration and asylum, solidarity refers to the principle that responsibility for managing migratory pressures should be shared among all Member States rather than borne exclusively by those located at the Union's external borders. Given the existence of a common external border, the management of migration constitutes a collective European responsibility. Nevertheless, geographical realities mean that frontline Member States, particularly Greece, Italy, Spain, Malta, and Cyprus, often receive a disproportionate share of arrivals of migrants and refugees.

As a result, these countries – and EU institutions – have long been advocating for solidarity mechanisms that would distribute responsibilities more equitably and support Member States experiencing significant migratory pressure.

Solidarity was implicit in asylum policies already in the 1999 Tampere Conclusions which stated in point 4 that the EU aimed to be “an open and secure European Union, fully committed to the obligations of the Geneva Refugee Convention [...] and able to respond to humanitarian needs on the basis of solidarity”.⁶ Article 63 of the Amsterdam Treaty provided for the “promotion of a balance of effort between Member States in receiving and bearing the consequences of receiving refugees and displaced persons”

⁶ Presidency Conclusions, Tampere European Council 15 and 16 October 1999.

without referring explicitly to the solidarity principle.

The ill-fated 2004 Constitutional Treaty was the first legal text to include an explicit provision on solidarity⁷ which, in 2009, became Article 80 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU), as part of the Lisbon Treaty. This legal basis states that Union policies concerning border controls, asylum, and immigration shall be governed by the principle of solidarity and the fair sharing of responsibility, including its financial implications. In practical terms, this principle may take the form of relocation measures, financial assistance, technical support, or operational assistance, such as asylum procedures support or border management through EU agencies such as Frontex and the European Union Agency for Asylum (EUAA).

4. The 2015 Migration Crisis and the Limits of Voluntary Solidarity

The migration crisis of 2015 exposed significant weaknesses within the Common European Asylum System, particularly the unfair allocation of responsibility

under the Dublin Regulation⁸. Under the Dublin system, responsibility for examining an asylum application ultimately, and unless other rules apply, falls upon the Member State of first irregular entry. This arrangement placed an additional burden on states that find themselves under particular migratory pressure because of their geographical location⁹ during periods of large-scale arrivals.

Following the arrival of more than one million migrants and asylum seekers in 2015, the Council of the European Union adopted emergency relocation schemes¹⁰ aimed at transferring 160,000 applicants for international protection from Greece and Italy (initially Hungary was also included, though the country eventually refused to participate in this measure) to other Member States. This marked the first large-scale attempt to operationalise solidarity through mandatory burden-sharing.

However, implementation proved highly problematic. By the end of the programme, 34,705 individuals had been relocated (12 706 from Italy and 21 999 from Greece) to 22 Member States and 3 associated

⁷ Article III-268 of the Constitutional Treaty provided that "the policies of the Union set out in this Section and their implementation shall be governed by the principle of solidarity and fair sharing of responsibility, including its financial implications, between the Member States. Whenever necessary, the Union acts adopted pursuant to this Section shall contain appropriate measures to give effect to this principle".

⁸ De Bruycker, P. (2024). "The new European solidarity mechanism: Towards a fair sharing of responsibility between member states?". Policy Study, Foundation for European Progressive Studies, Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung and European Policy Centre, Brussels. p.9

⁹ Varsamis Mitsilegas, Solidarity and Trust in the Common European Asylum System. CMS 2, (2014). p. 186 <https://doi.org/10.5117/CMS2014.2.MITS>

¹⁰ Council Decision (EU) 2015/1601 of 22 September 2015 establishing provisional measures in the area of international protection for the benefit of Italy and Greece and Council Decision (EU) 2015/1523 of 14 September 2015 establishing provisional measures in the area of international protection for the benefit of Italy and of Greece.

countries, representing only around 22 per cent of the original target.¹¹

In addition, some Member States (Poland, Hungary, and Slovakia) opposed the relocation mechanism and refused to participate. The resulting legal disputes culminated in a judgment of the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU), which found that these Member States had failed to fulfil their obligations under EU law by refusing to comply with the relocation decisions.¹² Although the practical effects of the ruling were limited because the relocation programme had already expired, the judgment reaffirmed the binding nature of solidarity measures adopted under EU law and, also, highlighted the tension between national sovereignty and collective responsibility. In addition, the conclusion by the Court that there has been infringement by a Member State may be relevant to the determination of the basis for any liability of that Member State for damages for infringement towards other Member States, the EU or other organisations, while the decision in question were in force.

¹¹ European Court of Auditors, Special Report No 24: Asylum, relocation and return of migrants: Time to step up action to address disparities between objectives and results. 2019 in https://www.eca.europa.eu/Lists/ECADocuments/SR19_24/SR_Migration_management_EN.pdf

¹² The Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) delivered two major judgments on the 2015 EU provisional refugee relocation scheme. First, in September 2017 (Joined Cases C-643/15 and C-647/15), the Court dismissed Hungary and Slovakia's challenges, legally validating the mandatory relocation quotas. Second, in April 2020 (Joined Cases C-715/17, C-718/17 and C-719/17, Commission v Poland, Hungary and the Czech Republic), the CJEU ruled that Hungary breached EU law by outright refusing to implement the mandatory relocation decisions.

5. The Voluntary Solidarity Mechanism

In the aftermath of the crisis, the Commission tried to reform the Common European Asylum System and in the first place the Dublin-III Regulation. However, no agreement could be reached in the Council as opinions diverged both among Member States in the Council and between the institutions. For the Member States of the South, the so-called people's solidarity, in other words solidarity expressed in the physical relocation of asylum seekers rather than financial support, was a *sine qua non* condition for accepting a reform of the Dublin system. Following several years of political deadlock, Member States restarted negotiations and sought alternative approaches to solidarity. In this context, in June 2022, twenty-one European countries endorsed the Voluntary Solidarity Mechanism (VSM) through a political declaration¹³ designed to support frontline Member States in the Mediterranean region. The mechanism focused primarily on voluntary relocations and other forms of assistance.¹⁴

The VSM was offered to the states of the Mediterranean (Spain, Italy, Malta, Greece and Cyprus) so that

¹³ First step in the gradual implementation of the European Pact on Migration and Asylum: modus operandi of a voluntary solidarity mechanism in https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/document/download/f86bec44-64d6-4f0d-8809-2520360b1482_en?filename=Declaration%20on%20solidarity_en.pdf

¹⁴ Sergio Carrera and Roberto Cortinovis, the Declaration on a Voluntary Solidarity Mechanism and EU asylum policy - One Step Forward, Three Steps Back on Equal Solidarity, CEPS, In-Depth Analysis, October 2022 – 04.

they would accept the Council general approach on the new Eurodac and on the screening regulation. The Declaration was described as 'temporary' and as a first step towards a more structured, compulsory form of solidarity. Although participation remained discretionary, the VSM represented an important attempt to rebuild trust among Member States and demonstrate that practical cooperation remained possible despite earlier disagreements. The first relocation transfers under the VSM started in August 2022. Since then, and up to September 2025, the Mechanism has ensured the transfer of almost 6,900 applicants from the five Mediterranean countries.¹⁵

By its conclusion in June 2026, when it was replaced by the permanent solidarity mechanism, the VSM served as a testing ground for several solidarity arrangements that were subsequently incorporated into the New Pact on Migration and Asylum.

6. The New Pact on Migration and Asylum

As stated above, the post-2016 stalemate in the discussions on the new asylum rules was broken after the new Commission came up with new legislative measures aiming to establish a comprehensive system of rules embracing asylum law, borders policy, legal migration, and the fight against smuggling, also including the external dimension of those policies. The New Pact on

Migration and Asylum¹⁶ as it was called, was negotiated as a package deal (it includes 10 legislative instruments), agreed between the two co-legislators in December 2023 and adopted in 2024; it entered into application on June 12, 2026.

Due to limitations of space, this policy brief does not analyse the Pact in its entirety, as it represents the most comprehensive reform of EU migration governance since the creation of the Common European Asylum System. What is of essence here is that the Pact, for the first time in the EU context, establishes a permanent solidarity framework intended to ensure that frontline Member States are not left to manage disproportionate migratory pressures alone.

The general framework for solidarity contributions is established in the Asylum and Migration Management Regulation (AMMR)¹⁷, while the Crisis and Force Majeure Regulation¹⁸ provides specific mechanisms for responding to exceptional migratory situations.

A central innovation of this new framework is the introduction of what is called "flexible solidarity".

¹⁶ European Commission, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on "A New Pact on Migration and Asylum Brussels," 23.9.2020, COM (2020) 609 final.

¹⁷ Regulation (EU) 2024/1351 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 May 2024 on asylum and migration management, amending Regulations (EU) 2021/1147 and (EU) 2021/1060 and repealing Regulation (EU) No 604/2013 OJ L, 2024/1351, 22.5.2024.

¹⁸ Regulation (EU) 2024/1359 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 May 2024 addressing situations of crisis and force majeure in the field of migration and asylum and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1147, OJ L, 2024/1359, 22.5.2024.

¹⁵ European Commission. (n.d.). Relocation: EU solidarity in practice. https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/migration-management/relocation-eu-solidarity-practice_en

Rather than imposing a single form of contribution, Member States may choose among different types of support, including:

- the relocation of asylum seekers or beneficiaries of international protection;
- financial contributions;
- operational and technical assistance;
- capacity-building measures and other forms of support.

Under this system, Member States have agreed to contribute to a mandatory annual solidarity pool but may choose not to participate through relocations but, instead, through financial support, calculated according to formulas established by EU legislation.

These provisions, therefore, seek to reconcile competing political preferences by allowing flexibility in the form of solidarity while preserving the principle that all Member States must contribute in some manner. Nevertheless, the Dublin logic of assigning primary responsibility to the country of first entry largely remains in place. Despite the replacement of Dublin III by the Asylum and Migration Management Regulation (AMMR), the Pact does not fundamentally alter the allocation of responsibility for asylum claims. As Thym argues¹⁹, the New Pact largely builds upon existing structures and seeks to reconcile solidarity with

the established responsibility framework rather than replacing it altogether. Consequently, questions persist regarding whether the reforms will sufficiently alleviate structural pressures on frontline states in the long term.

The AMMR establishes a detailed annual governance framework through which the European Commission assesses migration and asylum developments across the EU and determines whether a Member State requires solidarity support. Each year, the Commission publishes an Annual Migration Management Report, based on information from Member States, EU agencies and other relevant sources. The report evaluates migratory trends, asylum systems' capacity, reception conditions, and the overall preparedness of Member States. A Member State may be identified as being under migratory pressure when it faces a disproportionate number of arrivals, asylum applications, or search-and-rescue disembarkations relative to its population and economic capacity, or when its asylum, reception, or migration management systems are at risk of becoming overwhelmed. The Regulation also recognizes situations of significant migratory pressure and foreseeable pressure, allowing the Commission to take account not only of existing burdens but also of likely future developments based on risk assessments and migration forecasts. Following its assessment, the Commission determines the solidarity needs of the affected Member States and proposes the overall scale of the annual solidarity pool. Member States then indicate their preferred contributions, after which the Commission reviews whether the

¹⁹ Daniel Thym, *Never-Ending Story? Political Dynamics, Legislative Uncertainties, and Practical Drawbacks of the 'New' Pact on Migration and Asylum* in Thym, Daniel & Odysseus Academic Network. *Reforming the Common European Asylum System: Opportunities, Pitfalls, and Downsides of the Commission Proposals for a New Pact on Migration and Asylum*, Baden-Baden: Nomos, 2022.

pledges are sufficient and may organize a solidarity forum to address any shortfalls. This governance structure gives the Commission a central coordinating role, although the final implementation of solidarity measures remains largely in the hands of the Member States.

7. Findings from the first year of application of solidarity

The Pact entered into application in June 2026; consequently, solidarity should count from that date, too. As provided for in AMMR, the Commission issued, on 11 November 2025, its Asylum and Migration Report²⁰ and identified 4 Member States as being under migratory pressure (Greece and Cyprus due to the disproportionate level of arrivals over the previous year and Spain and Italy because of a disproportionate number of arrivals following search and rescue at sea). In addition, Bulgaria, Czechia, Estonia, Croatia, Austria and Poland were identified as facing a significant migratory situation and could ask the Council for a full or partial deduction from their contributions to the Solidarity Pool for the upcoming year.

The Report also included annexes with the Council proposals for the 'solidarity pool'. These proposals were agreed at the Council in December 2025; the "pool" that was established eventually included 21.000 relocations or 420 million euros in economic

contributions. Consequently, if a Member State refuses to offer relocations, they must pay approximately €20,000 per person.

Although the implementation period remains relatively short, several preliminary observations can be made.

First, the Pact's flexible solidarity framework represents a significant departure from earlier attempts to impose uniform relocation obligations. Mechanisms such as relocation offsets and alternative contributions provide Member States with greater discretion in determining how they fulfil their responsibilities. This flexibility may improve political acceptability and increase participation. On the downside, the first year saw an effort to settle old debts and start with a 'clean slate': two of the four Member States under migratory pressure (Italy and Greece) which had issues with other Member States on the basis of pending Dublin transfers, made bilateral arrangements with the latter (mainly France and Germany) to offset their relocation needs with these Dublin transfers. This so-called "reverse Dublin" and more generally the responsibility offset mechanisms allowed by AMMR change the nature of solidarity, which is transformed into an accounting system.

Secondly, early implementation indicates that Member States continue to favour financial and operational contributions over relocation commitments. This suggests that while solidarity has become more institutionalised, political sensitivities surrounding the relocation of asylum seekers remain significant. In addition, not all contributing Member States fully comply with this obligation, an

²⁰ European Commission, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council, The European Annual Asylum and Migration Report, Brussels, 11.11.2025, COM(2025) 795 final.

issue that the Commission, as the guardian of the Treaties, should deal with speedily.²¹

Thirdly, implementation challenges persist. Differences in administrative capacity, national political priorities, and varying interpretations of solidarity obligations continue to affect the effectiveness of the system. Consequently, the long-term success of the Pact will depend not only on its legal framework but also on sustained political commitment among Member States.

8. Conclusion

Given the limited period of implementation, any assessment of effectiveness must remain preliminary. More comprehensive evaluations will be possible only after several years of operation.

Solidarity has evolved from a general political aspiration into a legally recognised principle that shapes the functioning of the European Union. In the field of migration and asylum, this evolution has been particularly pronounced. The migration crisis of 2015 exposed the limitations of voluntary cooperation and demonstrated the need for more structured mechanisms of responsibility-sharing.

Subsequent developments, including the Voluntary Solidarity Mechanism and the New Pact on Migration and Asylum, reflect the Union's efforts to translate the principle of solidarity into concrete

policy instruments. While these reforms represent significant progress, important challenges remain regarding implementation, political acceptance, and the continued reliance on the country-of-first-entry principle.

Ultimately, the development of solidarity in EU migration policy illustrates the broader trajectory of European integration: an ongoing effort to balance national interests with collective responsibility. Whether the New Pact succeeds in creating a sustainable and equitable system will largely determine the future role of solidarity within the European Union's migration and asylum framework.

²¹ Florian Trauner et al. Towards a Fairer EU Asylum Policy: Lessons from the Dublin system for the EU's Solidarity Mechanism, Discussion Paper, European Policy Center (EPC). European Migration and Diversity Programme, 26 November 2025.

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